

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF MODERN DISTANCE LEARNING

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Abstract.

The article is devoted to the study of psychological and organizational features of distance learning in modern conditions of development of education at the university. The psychological characteristics of students, their difficulties during training are determined. The problems faced by teachers in the organization and implementation of distance learning are also clarified.

Keywords.

higher education, higher school, educational process, self-education, psychological and pedagogical features, personality, student, teacher, distance learning.

One of the modern requirements for the education system is attention to the student's individuality. Distance education allows students in modern social and economic conditions to become a well-educated person, able to flexibly restructure the content of their activities in accordance with the requirements of rapidly developing dentistry. Students studying in the distance education system are mainly engaged in professional self-development at a convenient time for them. Thus, distance education can be considered as a space for self-actualization of the individual. Distance learning is fundamentally different from traditional forms of learning. When considering distance learning as an activity mediated by computer technology, it should be noted that it is characterized by a number of psychological features compared to traditional forms of education. The use of computer technologies in the distance education of students makes it possible to improve its cognitive processes. The introduction of distance education fundamentally changes

the role positions of "*teacher-student*". In the traditional form of education, the teacher acts as an interpreter of knowledge. With the expansion of the educational space, the function of interpreting knowledge is assumed by the student, and the teacher is the coordinator of this knowledge. He advises students, directs the work of the student's cognitive processes, that is, takes on the functions of supporting the student's professional development [1]. Almost all developed countries consider the development of distance education a priority and annually allocate considerable funds for these programs. Naturally, the United States is ahead of the rest. Probably because in this country all the best have come together precisely for the development of this type of education.

Some experts in this field predict the further dominance of distance education over traditional forms of education and the complete replacement of the latter in the future. But, probably, this will not happen, just as happened with the replacement of theaters by the film industry, television, etc. The popularity of distance education is growing, as it has many advantages. First, mass. The number of persons enrolled in the same programs at the same university is determined only by the characteristics of the communication equipment. By the way, it was mass character and general accessibility that became the motivation for the emergence of distance education. The second advantage of distance education is "*speed*". The third is the relative cheapness of obtaining knowledge [2]. On average, getting a degree from a Western university will cost you about ten times less. However, there are still quite a few educational institutions that offer distance education in its purest form and in all specialties. But it all comes down to this.

So, in general, the main differences and advantages of distance learning from traditional forms of education are:

- *the ability to study at a convenient time, place and pace. An unregulated period of time for mastering the discipline;*
- *-training in parallel with professional activity, i.e. on the job;*
- *concentrated imagination of educational information and multi-access to it increases the efficiency of mastering the material;*
- *the use in the educational process of the latest achievements of information and telecommunication technologies teaches how to work with them;*
- *equal opportunities to receive education regardless of the place of residence, state of health, elitism and material security of the student;*
- *export and import of world achievements in the market of educational services;*

➤ *distance learning expands and updates the role of the teacher, who must coordinate the cognitive process, constantly improve the courses he teaches, increase creative activity and qualifications in accordance with innovations and innovations;*

➤ *distance education also has a positive effect on the student, increasing his creative and intellectual potential through self-organization, the pursuit of knowledge, the ability to interact with computer technology and make responsible decisions independently.*

In the complex of psychological features of distance learning, several groups can be distinguished that require special attention. First of all, this is the definition of the age range of students capable of distance learning and a description of the psychological characteristics of these students [3]. In our opinion, the currently available forms of distance learning are most suitable for adults receiving additional education or undergoing retraining, but with a certain refinement of work programs on the content of training, taking into account modern requirements, it is also possible to train university students, as evidenced by the results of our study. The formation of the integrity of the intellect is a long-term and contradictory process. B. Ananiev noted that the leading role in this process is played by education (the amount of acquired knowledge, the general level of information) and training (activities for the assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities). As a result of the complex studies carried out, B. G. Ananiev came to an important conclusion: in the course of the development of an adult, the degree of knowledge acquisition increases.

In foreign psychology, the problem of interrupting traditional distance learning is recognized by all and is being studied quite actively. The most influencing factor in the decision of students to continue or interrupt distance learning was satisfaction with communication with the teacher. In a study by Caskelly, Deneher, and Prunell, it was found that contact with the teacher is necessary for students not only to clarify obscure learning topics, but also to maintain motivation to learn and collaborate with classmates [4]. Thus, not only insufficient communication with the teacher affects the emergence of a desire to interrupt distance learning, limited communication with fellow students is essential. In a study by G. Astleitner and A. Sindler, conducted in 1999, it was revealed that, despite the fact that all students were satisfied with the content of the distance learning course, they considered the lack of emotional contacts with classmates and the inability to discuss emotional problems to be the main disadvantages of distance learning. For example, research conducted at the British Open University made it possible to determine the requirements for students and teachers: polite, respectful treatment; transparent and objective system of grades

and degrees; explanations and justifications for assessing the acquired knowledge; students' understanding of the meaning of grades [5].

So, students of distance learning indicated the presence of such educational problems:

➤ *the need for obtaining and consolidating knowledge in the specialty is not satisfied; the need for a better quality test of knowledge, the lack of assessment in the learning process. Lack of communication with the teacher. Students realize that the teacher is the most important translator of experience, without which professional socialization is impossible;*

➤ *the lack of creative self-realization of students in the process of distance learning.*

So, according to the results of the study, we came to the following conclusions:

1. A formal approach to the organization and implementation of the educational process in the distance learning system takes place in the "**zone of actual development**", which is unreasonably easy for students and loses its developmental effect.

2. The creators of "**cases**" are not significant people for students in the distance learning system.

3. The main reason for personal dissatisfaction with the distance learning system is the lack of communication with the teacher.

4. The personality of distance learning experiences difficulties in establishing contact in the context of the educational system; evaluates teachers significantly worse in terms of personal and professional qualities; cares little about his future profession, as if "**does not see**" himself in it.

5. There are no clearly expressed problems in the communication of distance learning students.

6. The level of subjective control (internal personal responsibility) of distance learning students does not differ from students of the traditional form of education at the university.

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